

What's the Proper Step? Improving Competencies for Greater Accountability through Procurement Personnel's Strategic Training, Education, and Professionalization (ProPer STEP) Program of Civil Service Commission Regional Office IV, Philippines

Atty. Karin Litz P. Zerna, Maria Leticia G. Reyna, MNSA, Melvin S. Domingo, EdD
kpzerna@csc.gov.ph; mgreyna@csc.gov.ph; msdomingo@csc.gov.ph
Civil Service Commission, Philippines

Abstract

Procurement practitioners play a vital role in promoting transparency and accountability in a government organization. Hence, they need to be adequately capacitated for them to effectively and efficiently perform their functions. The study identified the procurement practitioners' profile in terms of current position, educational qualification, length of experience, and training attended as well as their ICT skills and ethical behavior as independent variables. As a dependent variable, their level of competence in conducting public bidding, resorting to alternative modes of procurement, and preparing accountability reports was assessed. Relationship of variables was also tested.

This paper utilized a descriptive correlational study using surveys through Google forms. Data was processed through frequency, percentage, median, interquartile range, and Spearman's rank correlation using Excel application.

Data revealed that attendance to training and ICT skills are significantly related to the competence of the procurement practitioners. The findings support the crafting of the ProPer STEP Program, a six-year learning and development intervention for procurement practitioners which aims to professionalize its procurement practitioners to improve transparency and accountability in the organization.

Keywords: *procurement, training, ICT skills, learning and development*

1. INTRODUCTION

Procurement is the process of acquiring goods and services, infrastructure projects, and consulting services by a government agency (Government Procurement Reform Act, 2003). The funds used for the procurement is from the country's own revenues and from loans and grants from external banks or donors (Government of the Philippines[GoP], Asian Development Bank [ADB] & World Bank [WB], 2008). Since procurement involves the utilization of public funds, it must be carried out efficiently and with high ethical standards to promote public interest (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], n. d. b).

Procurement is considered to be the largest or second-largest category of expenditure in any organization (Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System, n. d.). Because of the huge amount of public funds involved in procurement, it remains to be a government activity susceptible to waste (OECD, n. d. a). It is therefore an important government undertaking in securing value for people's money (GoP, ADB & WB, 2008). This was also underscored in a study of Philippine Institute for Development Studies citing that value for money is met if officials and practitioners clearly understand the purpose of procurement (Navarro & Tanghal, 2017).

Those involved in the procurement must be professionalized in support of their procurement-related functions within six months upon their designation (Government

Procurement Reform Act, 2003). It was noted that those involved in procurement should be capacitated with the correct methods and practices in order for the procurement systems to be further improved. This is due to problems relating to dishonest officials and bidders (GoP, ADB & WB, 2008). Knowledge of the procurement system is vital for it guides the practitioners on how to properly conduct procurement activities and minimize non-compliance on relevant laws and rules (Si, 2017).

There has been no study in the Civil Service Commission Regional Office IV on the assessment of the level of competence of its procurement practitioners and what factors affect it. This study will therefore help the management address the competency gaps and decide what appropriate intervention to implement.

The main focus of this study was to determine what significantly relates with the level of staff competence of the procurement practitioners of CSCRO IV. Specifically, this study attempted to provide answers on the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the procurement practitioners in terms of their:
 - a. current position;
 - b. educational qualification;
 - c. length of experience as procurement practitioner; and
 - d. training related to procurement?
2. What is their level of ICT skills related to procurement?
3. What is the extent of manifestation of their ethical behavior?
4. What is the level of staff competence of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. public bidding;
 - b. alternative mode of procurement; and
 - c. accountability reports?
5. What is the relationship between the dependent variables and the independent variable?

This study is anchored on different laws and theories such as law of exercise, law of recency, theory of moral development, and theory of continuous improvement. The law of exercise states that the more a person practices something, that person becomes more able to retain the knowledge (Thorndike, 1932). It is assumed that if procurement practitioners have longer experience in procurement, have gained enough competence, and acquired ICT skills, they can be able to retain those competencies which they can use to perform their procurement-related duties. Likewise, the law of regency which refers to the tendency of the person recall the most recent event or experience (Thorndike, 1932). It is premised that if the procurement practitioners have recent experience, recent education, and recent training related to procurement, then he or she can be able to recall and use them in the discharge of functions. Further, Kohlberg's theory of moral development cites that as a person reaches adulthood, personal ethics becomes the basis of his or her moral reasoning (McLeod, 2023). It is assumed that the manifestation of personal ethics of a procurement practitioner relates to his or her level of competence. Lastly, this study centered on the theory of continuous improvement which deals with the undertakings of an organization in looking for better ways to do things. The small improvement helps in the improvement of products, services, and processes and tries to eliminate wastage and inefficiencies (Investors in People, 2019). The desired output of this study which is a developmental program is a manifestation of that desire to have a continuous improvement.

Based on the theories cited, the conceptual model of this study had been conceptualized as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

This study utilized the IV-DV model as its conceptual framework. The independent variables include the demographic profile, ICT skills, and ethical behavior of the procurement practitioners. Demographic profile will be assessed in terms of current position, educational qualification, length of experience, and training attended. On the other hand, the dependent variable is the staff competence in terms of public bidding, alternative mode of procurement, and accountability reports.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study used the correlational quantitative research design which sought to understand the relationship between the variables under study. It was conducted at the Civil Service Commission Regional Office IV, Quezon City, Philippines in May 2022 and updated in November 2023. The 33 respondents were randomly chosen from 35 procurement practitioners who are composed of the Bids and Awards Committee (BAC), its technical working group, secretariat, inspectors, end-users, and the finance personnel.

A researcher-made questionnaire was used as the primary instrument to gather the necessary data. To establish its validity, expertise of procurement personnel from other government agencies was sought. Their suggestions were incorporated on the final version of the said instrument. For reliability testing, it was administered to select procurement practitioners from national government agencies. It obtained a Cronbach's alpha of .94 which is considered excellent. To facilitate timely and efficient data gathering, this was administered through a Google form. The link of which was sent to the respondents which they answered through their smartphones, desktops, or laptops. Frequency, percentage, median, and interquartile range were the descriptive statistics used. Since all variables were transformed into ordinal data, the Spearman's rank correlation was used to test their relationship.

3. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

3.1 Demographic Profile of Procurement Practitioners

The organization was well represented by procurement practitioners from different levels of position. The number of those holding at least a technical position (87.88%) could be a strong indication that the assigned personnel can navigate through the technicalities and complexities of the procurement works. Mansi and Pandey (2016) cited that position in the

organization was a factor that could predict sustainable procurement practices. Likewise, the respondents had varied educational qualifications. Almost half of them (48.48%) acquired at least a master's degree which could be an assurance that they can understand the laws, policies, rules, and regulations of procurement. Mutesi and Safari (2021) cited that educational level has a significant impact on procurement performance. Data also shows that only one out of four personnel (24.24%) had enough experience on procurement which implies that majority were new in the procurement work. Experience was a factor identified contributing to the procurement performance of an organization (Eliah & Athumani, 2020). Further, almost one-third (30.30%) of the respondents had no training on procurement in the last three years. L&D is vital among the employees because it helps them accomplish their tasks in an effective and efficient manner (Rodriguez & Walters, 2017). Training was one factor identified affecting the procurement proficiency (Eliah & Athumani, 2020; Muriuki & Odari, 2018; Truitt, 2011). The Civil Service Commission (2017) emphasized that continuous L&D shall be implemented by all government agencies. It underscored that each employee should be given an opportunity to undergo at least one planned L&D during the year.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Procurement Practitioners

Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percentage
<i>Current position</i>				
Managerial/Executive	10	30.30	10	30.30
Supervisory	6	18.18	16	48.48
Technical	13	39.39	29	87.88
Clerical	4	12.12	33	100.00
<i>Educational qualification</i>				
Doctorate degree	5	15.15	5	15.15
Master's degree	11	33.33	16	48.48
Bachelor's degree	16	48.48	32	96.96
College undergraduate	1	3.03	33	100.00
<i>Length of experience</i>				
10 years and above	4	12.12	4	12.12
More than 5 years but below 10 years	4	12.12	8	24.24
5 years and below	25	75.76	33	100.00
<i>Training attended</i>				
No training	10	30.30	10	30.30
8 hours and below	11	33.33	21	63.6.3
More than 8 hours but less than 40 hours	12	36.36	33	100.00

3.2 ICT Skills

In terms of ICT skills needed for procurement, the procurement practitioners, however, acknowledged that they had adequate competency ($Mdn=3$) as reflected in Table 2. These competencies include using desktop or laptop ($Mdn=3$), document scanning ($Mdn=3$), preparing slides ($Mdn=3$), using digital or electronic signature ($Mdn=3$), using email ($Mdn=3$), and using videoconferencing tools ($Mdn=3$). This high competency can be attributed to the ongoing digitization and digitalization efforts of the Civil Service Commission. ICT was identified as a factor which could affect the procurement performance and efficiency (Awoke & Singh, 2020; Muriuki & Odari, 2018; Wanyonyi & Muturi, 2015).

Table 2: ICT Skills

ICT Skills	Median	Interquartile Range	Interpretation
Using desktop computer or laptop in encoding, storing, and printing procurement documents	3	1	Adequate competency
Scanning of procurement documents for digitization purposes	3	1	Adequate competency
Preparing slides for presentation purposes (<i>e.g. Powerpoint, Slidesgo, Canva, etc.</i>)	3	1	Adequate competency
Using/affixing digital or electronic signature for procurement documents	3	1	Adequate competency
Using email as a means of communication with end-users, procurement practitioners, clients, and others concerned	3	1	Adequate competency
Using videoconferencing tools in attending procurement activities (<i>e.g. Zoom, MS Teams, Google Meet, etc.</i>)	3	1	Adequate competency
Overall	3	1	Adequate competency

3.3 Ethical Behavior

As reflected in Table 3, the respondents claimed to have demonstrated to a high extent the ethical behavior expected of a public procurement practitioner ($Mdn=4$). They said that they highly manifested the following competencies: neutrality for bidders ($Mdn=4$), integrity at work ($Mdn=4$), confidentiality on bidding information ($Mdn=4$), privacy on results ($Mdn=4$), and impartiality on decision making ($Mdn=4$). It has been noted that employee ethics is a factor which can affect the procurement performance (Awoke & Singh, 2020; Muriuki & Odari, 2018; Wanyonyi & Muturi, 2015).

Table 3: Ethical Behavior

Ethical Behavior	Median	Interquartile Range	Interpretation
Does not make preference for bidders by virtue of kinship, acquaintance, scope of business operations, etc.	4	0	Highly manifested
Does not accept monetary and non-monetary gifts from the bidders.	4	0	Highly manifested
Does not disclose relevant information to the bidders that would give them advantage over their competitors.	4	0	Highly manifested
Does not make or accept any communication with any bidder regarding the evaluation of their bids until the issuance of the Notice of Award.	4	0	Highly manifested
Does not render a decision that would give undue favor to a certain bidder.	4	0	Highly manifested
Overall	4	0	Highly manifested

3.4 Staff Competence

As shown in Table 4, the overall level of competence of the procurement practitioners was inadequate. They had inadequate competency on public bidding ($Mdn=2$) and alternative modes of procurement ($Mdn=2$). Notably, respondents gained enough knowledge and skills in preparing the accountability reports ($Mdn=3$). This can be attributed to their active involvement in the submission of regular procurement reports to the Regional Office which has become a performance target of the office and individuals concerned.

Table 4: Staff Competence

Staff Competence	Median	Interquartile Range	Interpretation
Public bidding	2	1	Inadequate competency
Alternative modes of procurement	2	2	Inadequate competency
Accountability reports	3	1	Adequate competency
Overall	2	1	Inadequate competency

3.5 Relationship of Variables

Table 5 presents the correlation of the variables under study. Of the four demographic variables, only the training attended by the respondents was found to have significant relationship with other variables. It had moderate positive correlation with staff competence in terms of conducting alternative modes of procurement, $r(31) = .55, p = .001$, and preparing accountability reports, $r(31) = .54, p = .001$, while it had low positive correlation with staff competence in terms of conducting public bidding, $r(31) = .36, p = .038$. This indicates that as the training hours of a practitioner increases, his or her level of competence in procurement also increases. This supports the findings of Eliah and Athumani (2020), Muriuki and Odari (2018), and Truitt (2011). Further, ICT skills of the practitioners were found to have a strong positive correlation with staff competence in terms of preparing the accountability reports,

$r(31) = .64$, $p = .001$, while it had a low positive correlation with staff competence in terms of conducting alternative modes of procurement, $r(31) = .38$, $p = .029$. This implies that as the level of ICT skills of the practitioner increases, his or her level of competence in procurement also increases. This corroborates with the findings of Awoke and Singh (2020), Muriuki and Odari (2018), and Wanyonyi & Muturi (2015).

On the other hand, the current position was found to have no significant relationship with staff competence. This contradicts the findings of Mansi and Pandey (2016). Educational qualification was not also significantly correlated with staff competence which negates the findings of Mutesi and Safari (2021). There was no established significant relationship between length of experience and staff competence which is contrary to the findings of Eliah and Athumani (2020). Lastly, ethical behavior was not significantly related to the staff competence which counters the findings of Awoke and Singh (2020), Muriuki and Odari (2018), and Wanyonyi and Muturi (2015).

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation for Study Variables

Variable	N	Mdn	IQR	Public Bidding	Alternative Modes of Procurement	Accountability Reports
1. Current position	33	2	2	.093	.560	.586
2. Educational qualification	33	2	1	.239	.867	.865
3. Length of experience	33	1	0	.862	.846	.597
4. Training attended	33	2	2	.038*	.001*	.001*
5. ICT skills	33	3	1	.076	.029*	.001*
6. Ethical behavior	33	4	0	.990	.538	.427

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The procurement practitioners of CSC RO IV are diverse in terms of position and are educationally qualified. They are considered to be novice in procurement and have basic knowledge on it.
2. The respondents are ICT literate and they use their skills in performing their procurement functions.
3. The practitioners are just, fair, impartial, and conscientious in their dealings in procurement.
4. The respondents have a low level of competence in procurement.
5. Attendance in training and ICT skills significantly contribute to improving the competence of personnel involved in procurement.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the foregoing conclusions, the following are the recommendations:

1. As training significantly correlates with staff competence, CSCRO IV may consider sending its procurement practitioners to various L&D interventions for them to acquire significant knowledge and skills on procurement and keep abreast with the changes on procurement laws, rules, guidelines, and practices. These L&D interventions should be progressive, developmental, and designation specific so as to develop a pool of procurement experts. The attached intervention titled “Procurement Personnel’s Strategic Training, Education, and Professionalization Program” or “Proper STEP Program” may be adopted by the agency for implementation. The program will help the management of the CSCRO IV in deciding what L&D intervention procurement personnel should undergo in the next six years. By doing so, the CSCRO IV will create a pool of procurement practitioners who are highly-capacitated in their functions and observing the highest ethical standard on procurement as a product of a comprehensive professionalization program. Structured employee development programs help the organization retain its human resource, especially those who have wide experience in their field (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013). A continuous and active capacity building for procurement practitioners is an important venture which agencies need to invest on. This is a vital preparatory activity before an actual procurement is made (Navarro & Tanghal, 2017). Agencies therefore should invest in training for the employees to have superior knowledge on procurement (Turga, 2019). Moreover, orientation and re-orientation of new and existing procurement employees on policies and procedures were also recommended as an important intervention (Lupian-Poliran & Khanser, 2015).
2. Since ICT skills have a significant relationship with staff competence, CSCRO IV may consider strengthening its current digitization and digitalization efforts. Awoke and Singh (2020) recommended that investment on ICT infrastructure be undertaken to improve procurement performance. Likewise, Bekele (2015) cited that use of ICT in procurement could be maximized to enhance efficiency, effectiveness, and transparency.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to extend their warmest gratitude to all the officials and employees of CSCRO IV who took part in this study. Special thanks to the CSC Chairperson Atty. Karlo Alexei B. Nograles, CSC Commissioner Atty. Ryan Alvin R. Acosta, and CSC Commissioner Atty. Aileen Lourdes A. Lizada for the endorsement of this paper through the Office for Human Resource Management and Development (OHRMD) headed by Acting Director IV Atty. Rosalita B. Rances-Petaca, to the 3rd Conference on “Learning and Development to Support Good Governance” of the Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar).

REFERENCES

1. A. M. Navarro and J. O. Tanghal, *The promises and pains in procurement reforms in the Philippines*. Discussion Paper Series No. 2017-16. Philippine Institute of Development Studies (April 2017), <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1716.pdf>.

2. C. B. Si, "Knowledge of the procurement system and its relationship to completion of transaction in a government agency in Iloilo City," Unpublished thesis, Central Philippine University, 2017, <https://repository.cpu.edu.ph/handle/20.500.12852/1624>.
3. Civil Service Commission, 2017 Omnibus Rules on Appointments and Other Human Resource Actions, MC No. 24, s. 2017, Philippines (24 August 2017).
4. D. L. Truitt, The effect of training and development on employee attitude as it relates to training and work proficiency. *SAGE Open* (2011), <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F2158244011433338>.
5. E. A. Eliah and H. I. Athumani, The influence of staff competency on performance of procurement management units in Tanzanian training institutions: Case study of vocational education and training authority. *Internal Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 8(12), 372-383 (December 2020) <https://ijecm.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/81222.pdf>.
6. E. Thorndike, *The Fundamentals of Learning* (Teachers College Press, New York, 1932).
7. J. Rodriguez and K. Walters, The importance of training and development in employee performance and evaluation. *World Wide Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 3(10), 206-212 (2017), https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Kelley_Walters/publication/332537797_The_Importance_of_Training_and_Development_in_Employee_Performance_and_Evaluation/links/5cefe41092851c4dd01ba833/The-Importance-of-Training-and-Development-in-Employee-Performance-and-Evaluation.pdf.
8. Government of the Philippines, Asian Development Bank and World Bank, *Philippines: Country procurement assessment report* (3 October 2008), <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/7837>.
9. Government Procurement Reform Act, Rep. Act No. 9184, Philippines (10 January 2003), <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2003/01/10/republic-act-no-9184/>.
10. H. Mutesi and E. Safari, The impact of staff competence on procurement performance in public procurement in Rwanda: A case of Rwanda Public Procurement Authority, *International Journal of Advanced Scientific Research and Management*, 6(7), 25-31 (July 2021), <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/5864/impact%20of%20strategic%20procurement%20-%20Most%20updated%2013-11-2010-%20E.pdf?sequence=2>.
11. Investors in People, *Continuous improvement models: four great options for you*, (28 January 2019), <https://www.investorsinpeople.com/knowledge/continuous-improvement-models-four-great-options-for-you/#:~:text=is%20continuous%20improvement%3F,Continuous%20improvement%20is%20a%20mindset%20whereby%20organisations%20strive%20to%20always,optimal%20and%20efficient%20over%20time>.
12. K. Jehanzeb and N. A. Bashir, Training and development program and its benefits to employee and organization: A conceptual study. *European Journal of Business and Management*, (5)2, 243-253 (2013), <https://www.dcvmn.org/IMG/pdf/3947-5999-1-pb.pdf>.
13. M. C. Muriuki and S. Odari, Factors affecting procurement performance measurement in tertiary technical training institutes in Meru County, Kenya. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Information Technology*, 4(10), 610-623 (October 2018) <https://www.ijssit.com/main/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Factors-Affecting-Procurement-Performance-Measurement-In-Tertiary-Technical-Training-Institutes.pdf>.

14. M. Mansi and R. Pandey, Impact of demographic characteristics of procurement professionals on sustainable procurement practices: Evidence from Australia, *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 22(1), 31-40 (March 2016), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2015.06.001>.
15. OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development), *OECD support on public procurement* (n. d. a), <https://www.oecd.org/gov/public-procurement/support/>.
16. OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development), *Public procurement*, (n. d. b), <https://www.oecd.org/governance/public-procurement/>.
17. PhilGEPS (Philippine Government Electronic Procurement System), *PhilGEPS – government’s tool for procurement reforms and transparency* (n. d.).
18. S. C. Wanyonyi and W. Muturi, Factors affecting performance of procurement function among public technical, training institutions in Kisumu County, Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(5), 325-337 (May 2015), <https://ijecm.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/3520.pdf>.
19. S. L. Lupian-Poliran and M. Khanser, Procurement processes in a state university in Mindanao: A case study, *National Business and Management Conference*, 377-395 (2015), <https://nbmconference.files.wordpress.com/2017/11/383-401.pdf>.
20. S. Mcleod, *Kohlberg’s stages of moral development* (24 October 2003), <https://www.simplypsychology.org/kohlberg.html>.
21. T. Awoke and A. Singh, Factors Affecting the Effective Functioning of Public Procurement in Public Universities of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 8(6), 2095-2102 (March 2020), <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.f7995.038620>.
22. T. Turga, Factors affecting procurement performance of organization: The case of International Organization for Migration, Ethiopia Office, Addis Ababa University (2019), <http://etd.aau.edu.et/handle/123456789/20225>.
23. Z. Bekele, “Factors affecting procurement performance of public higher education institutions: The case of Jimma University,” Unpublished thesis, Jimma University, 2015. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/43540847.pdf>.